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Approaches to Evaluation of Training and Development in Banks: An Empirical Study

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This paper was set to examine the approaches to training and development in the banking sector. In line with the assertion made by the literature and the evidences gathered in the process of the study, the following recommendations were made: It is an established fact that the Kirkpatrick approach is widely used, it's the systematic training and development of personnel on continuous basis that can harness the totality of human resources in the organization, banks should ensure that any training and development approach which takes place is based on proper analysis of its contribution to the effectiveness and efficiency of banking industry. The data collected from different sources was cross checked. Different statistical tools and techniques were used like mean, mode, median, averages, t-test and chi-square. The paper concluded that most of training and development approaches used in the banking industry are that of Kirkpatrick. Each employer who invests seriously in the area of Training and Development needs to understand the approach to use in order to reap the benefits of an enriched working environment with higher levels of staff retention as well as increased productivity and performance. New entrants into organizations have various skills, though not all are relevant to organizational needs, hence the right approach to T&D is crucial. Right approaches to T and D are required for Human Resources to enable them work towards taking the organization to its expected destination. It is against this backdrop of the relative importance of approaches to evaluation of training and development in banks that this paper addressed.

Keywords: Approaches, Competitiveness, training and development and human resources.

Introduction

Evaluation is the process of systematically collecting information and using the information to determine the effects and value of training programme. It seeks to determine the degree to which the programme has done what it was supposed to do. Evaluation ensures that T&D programmes are accountable and are

meeting the needs of employees and the organization in the most cost-effective manner (Beardwell I and Holden, 1994).

Evaluation involves measurement in social as well as financial terms, which may be tangible for external training programmes. Evaluating training programmes is in fact an attempt to match the actual details of

programme with the “standard” that should happen. Evaluation is the process of systematically collecting information and using the information to determine the effects and value of training programme. It seeks to determine the degree to which the programme has done what it was supposed to do.

Approaches of Evaluation of Training

Here an attempt is made to study the approaches that are used by the banking industry while evaluating training. There are two approaches for clarification for the purpose which evaluation is intended to serve as shown in the table below.

Table 1 Approaches of evaluation of training in banks

Approaches	Respondents						Total
	Public Banks			Private Banks			
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
Expediency Approach	4 (57.1)	3 (42.9)	7 (100)	4 (50.0)	4 (50.0)	8 (100)	15 (50.0)
Interest of stakeholders	4 (50.0)	4 (50.0)	8 (100)	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)	7 (100)	15 (50.0)
Total	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	15 (100)	7 (46.7)	8 (53.3)	15 (100)	30 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

Table 1 shows approaches of evaluation of training in banks. 50 percent of the managers, 57.1 male and 42.9 percent female public banks managers and 50 percent each male and female managers of the private banks managers opined that expediency approach which assumes that a given activity task is problematic and needs to generate some information to show its value. The managers further observed that in this approach trainee are given a self - diagnostic questionnaire which help to make decision on evaluating a particular programme. 50 percent of the rest of the managers, 50 percent each male and female public banks managers and 42.9 percent male and 57.1 percent female managers cited that interest of stakeholder’s approach is

considered. This approach they said is based on two principles. First, it is to identify the main stakeholders of evaluation and analyze their different objectives towards evaluation. For example, trainees are likely to be interested in learning while the policy makers are more concerned about improving and controlling. Second, different objectives of the main stakeholders need to be communicated and negotiated during the whole process in order to reach a balanced view of priorities about evaluation. As shown from the analysis above responses of the managers on the approaches that the banking industry uses in evaluating training, it can be inferred that both approaches are given equal representation while evaluating training.

Table 2

Age and Opinions of Respondents about who is Responsible for Evaluation of Training

Age	Respondents								Total
	Public Banks				Private Banks				
	Individual	Manager	Training Department	Total	Individual	Manager	Training Department	Total	
20-30	8 (24.2)	14 (42.4)	11 (33.3)	33 (100)	5 (14.3)	9 (25.7)	21 (60.0)	35 (100)	68 (6.8)
31-40	21 (6.0)	79 (22.5)	251 (71.5)	351 (100)	16 (6.7)	62 (25.8)	162 (67.5)	240 (100)	591 (59.1)
41-50	3 (1.0)	98 (33.7)	190 (65.3)	291 (100)	8 (3.9)	80 (38.5)	120 (57.7)	208 (100)	499 (49.9)
ABOVE 51	1 (4.6)	11 (50.0)	10 (45.5)	22 (100)	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	6 (100)	28 (2.8)
Total	33 (5.9)	202 (36.1)	462 (82.5)	560 (100)	31 (7.1)	153 (34.7)	305 (69.3)	440 (100)	1000 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

Note: Some of the respondents gave more than two answers

Table 2 shows age and opinions of the respondents about who is responsible for evaluating training in the banking industry. It can be inferred that 59.1 percent of the total respondents were in the age group of 31-40, 49.9 percent were in the age group of 41-50, 6.8 percent were in the age group of 20-30 and 2.8 percent were age group of above 51. It can be further inferred that 82.5 percent of the public respondents and 69.3 percent of the private banks respondents opined that the responsibility of evaluating training rests on training department. They further opined that the Staff Development Plan template requires Training Departments to annually set out their planned staff development activities and an explanation of how they will be evaluated. 36.1 percent of the public banks respondents and 34.7 percent of the private banks respondents opined that the

responsibility for evaluating training in the banking industry rests on the manager/superior. They further observed that the manager is responsible for ensuring that staff has identified learning objectives for any development activity they plan to undertake and to agree on the methods to be used to evaluate training. The manager should have a discussion with the member of staff after the development activity has taken place to discuss the learning and to identify ways in which the application of the learning to the job can be assessed. The manager should ensure that training undertaken during the year is reviewed and evaluated. The last group as opined by the respondents on whom the responsibility for evaluating training rests as opined by 5.9 percent of the public banks respondents and 7.1 percent of the private banks respondents is an individual himself. It was observed

that the bank's Staff Development Application Form and Record requires individuals to identify their objectives linked to strategic development and training priorities and job role for the requested development activity. A discussion between the individual and their manager after the development activity has

taken place should enable an assessment of whether the learning objectives were met. Ongoing discussions between the manager and individual will allow for an assessment of whether the individual has been able to transfer the learning to the job after a reasonable timescale.

Table 3

Sex and Opinions of Managers about Reasons for Evaluating Training Programme

Reasons	Respondents						Total
	Public Banks			Private Banks			
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
To see how future programs can be improved	4 (57.1)	3 (42.9)	7 (100)	3 (50.0)	3 (50.0)	6 (100)	13 (43.3)
To determine whether training should be continued	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	5 (100)	9 (30.0)
To justify the existence of the training department	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	8 (26.7)
Total	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	15 (100)	7 (46.7)	8 (53.3)	15 (100)	30 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

Table 3 shows sex and opinions of managers about reasons for evaluating training programme. It can be inferred that 43.3 percent of the total respondents, 57.1 percent male and 42.9 percent female public respondents and 50 percent each male and female private banks managers observed that the reasons for evaluating training is to see how future programs can be improved. 30.0 percent of total managers, 50 each male and female respondents and 50 percent each male and female respondents of private banks opined that the reasons for evaluating training programme is to determine whether training should be continued. The rest of the total respondents

26.7 percent, 50 percent each male and female public managers and 50 percent each private bank respondent observed that the reasons for evaluating training programmes are to justify the existence of the training department.

The reasons for managers evaluating level four were because; the final results are more quantifiable in nature both for the trainers and the trainees. This helps the authorities to take decisions about the continuation of training in a very proactive manner as a result of quantifiable outcomes. Some of those quantifiable results are shown in the table as mentioned by the managers.

Table 4

Sex and Opinions of Managers about Quantifiable Results for Evaluating Level Four

	Respondents	

Quantifiable Results	Public Banks			Private Banks			Total
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
Increased production	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	8 (26.7)
Improved quality and decreased costs	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	3 (100)	7 (23.3)
Reduced frequency and/or severity of accidents	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	3 (100)	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	7 (23.3)
Reduced turnover and higher profits	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100)	8 (26.7)
Total	7 (46.7)	8 (53.3)	15 (100)	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	15 (100)	30 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

At this level the final impact results are taken into consideration. The final results can be in the form of increased production (26.7), improved quality and decreased costs (23.3), reduced frequency and/or severity of accidents (23.3), decreased costs, increased sales, reduced turnover and higher profits (26.7). It would help if the

final objectives of the training programme can be stated in these terms, for seeing improvement in the long-term. This assessment can be made between one to three years after completion of training, because otherwise there is a danger of 'lack of recall as opine by managers of the banking industry'.

Table 5: Sex and Opinions of Respondents about Objectives of Evaluating Impact of Training Programmes

Objectives of assessing the impact of the training	Respondents						Total
	Public Banks			Private Banks			
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
To understand the impact of training	99 (54.7)	82 (45.3)	181 (100)	80 (57.1)	60 (42.9)	140 (100)	321 (32.1)
To understand how training affected participant's	101 (56.1)	79 (43.9)	180 (100)	70 (46.7)	80 (53.3)	150 (100)	330 (33.0)
To understand the efficacy of institutionalizing an evaluation process	113 (56.8)	86 (43.2)	199 (100)	80 (53.3)	70 (46.7)	150 (100)	349 (34.9)
Total	313 (55.9)	247 (44.1)	560 (100)	230 (52.3)	210 (47.7)	440 (100)	1000 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

Table 5 shows sex and opinions of respondents about objectives of evaluating impact of training programmes. The respondents opined that the banks evaluated training programmes and get a macro picture across all the training programmes and all participants. It can be observed that 34.9 percent of the total respondents, 54.7 percent male and 45.3 percent female public respondents and 57.1 percent male and 42.9 percent female respondents of private banks cited that objectives of evaluating the impact of the training programmes is to understand the efficacy of institutionalizing an evaluation process using the KP model. 33.0 percent of the total respondents, 56.1 percent male and

43.9 percent female public banks and 46.7 percent male and 53.3 percent female private banks respondents observed that the objectives of evaluating the impact of the training programmes is to understand whether the training programmes had affected participant's performance in the work environment. The rest of the total respondents 32.1 percent, 54.7 percent male and 45.3 percent female public banks and 57.1 percent male and 42.9 percent female private banks respondents opined that the objectives of evaluating the impact of the training programmes is to understand the impact of training on the participant's knowledge, skills and attitudes.

Table 6 Age and Opinions of Employees about Professional Relevance of Training

Professional relevance of training	Age										Total
	Public					Private					
	20-30	31-40	41-50	Above 51	Total	20-30	31-40	41-50	Above 51	Total	
Program content	11 (6.2)	110 (61.5)	57 (31.8)	1 (0.6)	179 (100)	15 (11.0)	63 (46.3)	57 (41.9)	1 (0.7)	136 (100)	315 (30.5)
Practical application	11 (5.9)	100 (53.3)	73 (39.0)	3 (1.6)	187 (100)	9 (7.9)	58 (50.9)	45 (39.5)	2 (1.8)	114 (100)	301 (30.1)
Benefits of training	6 (4.7)	60 (47.2)	57 (44.9)	4 (3.2)	127 (100)	13 (12.5)	48 (46.2)	41 (39.4)	2 (1.9)	104 (100)	231 (23.1)
Ability to share the information	4 (6.0)	37 (55.2)	25 (32.8)	1 (1.5)	67 (100)	7 (8.1)	53 (61.6)	25 (29.1)	1 (1.2)	86 (100)	153 (15.3)
Total	32 (5.7)	307 (54.8)	212 (37.9)	9 (1.6)	560 (100)	44 (10.0)	222 (50.5)	168 (38.2)	6 (1.4)	440 (100)	1000 (100)

Source: Field survey (Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage row total)

Fig 1(a) and 2(b)

Table 6 and figure 1 shows the age and opinions of respondents about what they perceive as professional relevance of training. As the participants were heterogeneous in nature of i.e. age (20-30, 31-40, 41-50 and above 51) differences and sometimes working in different departments, 30.1 percent of the respondents opined that they could not implement what they had been trained in. The most common reasons for this shortcoming was that: (i) the training was not always relevant to the specific areas of

work, (ii) tools and techniques shown during the training did not exist in the work environment, and /or (iii) the training program did not cover issues of 'how to resolve the problem' which arose in the branch and (iv) after training, the trainee was shifted to another area of work, even if working in the same department. All these were cited as the reasons for not implementing the practical application. 23.1 percent of the total respondents observed that with regards to the benefit of training, it is interesting to note that the respondents

had an increased awareness through the program. The respondents were asked to rank the benefits of training, on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 standing for 'extremely useful' to 1 for 'not at all useful'. The benefits being: (1) improvement in inter personal relations, (2) New concepts / ideas introduced, (3) Increased efficiency in delivery of service were cited by the respondents as the benefits received. The rest of the respondents 15.3 percent observed that ability to share the information was less among the employees. The questionnaire had a separate part on "Professional relevance of training" which tried to understand the Level 3 and Level 4

attributes of change and results of training. The components included the relevance of Program content, extent of practical application of the program, benefits of training, ability to share the information received and change in organizational performance. The focused interviews helped in understanding whether the participant observed any perceptible change in his/her knowledge, skill, and attitudes after the training program. The trainees were also asked to identify how the learning could be utilized in the work situation. The survey clearly showed that the 30.5 percent of the total respondents opined that the program content had high relevance.

Table 7 Opinions of Respondents about Ways to Improve Training Programs at Level 3 and Level 4

Ways to Improve Training Programs at Level 3 and Level 4	Sex of Respondent						
	Public			Private			Total
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
The calendar of training be communicated	88 (54.7)	73 (45.3)	161 (100)	57 (54.3)	48 (45.7)	105 (100)	266 (26.6)
Selection of participants to be done with an objective	81 (55.1)	66 (44.9)	147 (100)	54 (58.7)	38 (41.3)	92 (100)	239 (23.9)
Scrutinize the nominations sent	61 (52.6)	55 (47.4)	116 (100)	51 (53.1)	45 (46.9)	96 (100)	212 (21.2)
Participants needs a program guide	37 (53.6)	32 (46.4)	69 (100)	41 (59.4)	28 (40.6)	69 (100)	138 (13.8)
Impact of training programs to be evaluated	37 (55.2)	30 (44.8)	67 (100)	44 (56.4)	34 (43.6)	78 (100)	145 (14.5)
Total	304 (54.3)	256 (45.7)	560 (100)	247 (56.1)	193 (43.9)	440 (100)	1000 (100)

Source: Field Survey (Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage to row total)

Fig 2(a) and 3(b)

Table 8 shows the opinions of respondents about ways to improve training programs at level 3 and level 4. It can be inferred that 26.6 percent of the total respondents, 54.7 percent male and 45.3 percent female public banks respondents and 54.3 percent male and 45.7 percent female private banks respondents opined that most of the participants were unaware of the gamut of training programmes offered by the training centres/Institutions. It was suggested that if the calendar of the training programs were communicated to the concerned Department a year in advance then the participants could choose those training programmes which would be most relevant

to them. 23.9 percent of the total respondents, 55.1 percent male and 44.9 percent female public banks respondents and 58.7 percent male and 41.3 percent female private banks respondents opined that the selection of participants had to be done in an objective manner by the branches or departments, which is sending the participants; based on the relevance of the training program. Younger personnel with more years in service would have to be sent for training. The other way to improve the training programmes in these levels as cited by the respondents 21.2 percent, 52.6 percent male and 47.4 percent female public banks respondents and 53.1 percent male

and 46.9 percent female private banks respondents observed that the training institution/centres would have to scrutinize the nominations sent, through its own rigorous protocol for selection of the participants. This way the right participant who is well experienced in a relevant field would get enough inputs for betterment. 14.5 percent of the total respondents, 55.2 percent male and 44.8 percent female public banks respondents and 56.4 percent male and 43.6 percent female private banks

respondents observed that every group of participants needs a programme guide from the parent department to help them through the training programme. The rest of the total respondents 13.8 percent, 53.6 percent male and 46.4 percent female public banks respondents and 59.4 percent male and 43.6 percent female private banks respondents observed that the impact of training programmes to be evaluated within 3-6 months after training programme to help recap the learning.

SUGGESTIONS

1. There is consensus about the importance of evaluation of training among the surveyed departments. However differences are recognized between the groups about the purposes and approaches of evaluation are identified in respect to the position of individual department.
2. A greater importance need to be given to evaluation since this is the only acid test available to management to know whether training served the purposes which it was intended to do in the first place. Therefore, it's essential to know beforehand what is to be expected from training and how this expectation is to be measured in tangible terms. Without the conviction and will for this, training would just be a wasteful effort.
3. Evaluation of training has not to take place only at one or two level which makes it meaningless and

superficial. Finding out the immediate reaction of the trainees and observing them during training programmers are certainly the most popular evaluation methods but they just prove that training experience was pleasant and nothing more. Testing whether training, as a process of unfreezing, new learning and refreezing experience has percolated down the knowledge, attitude and skill level is essential for evaluation.

4. Measuring the impact of training at one or two levels arbitrarily does not contribute to meaningful evaluation. There has to be a compressive evaluation procedure to be used at different levels by use of variety of methods available.
5. Feedback should be taken from the trainees after the training is over, so that the organization comes to know about the deficiencies in the training program & also suggestions to improve upon the same.

Conclusions

Business conducting and survival in the present day turbulent environment are relying on organizational knowledge in a sense of a giving timely and appropriate answer to challenges. The ability of individuals and organizations to obtain and master new knowledge has become the key comparative advantage. The concept of knowledge management and management of human resources, especially the function of employee training and development within the learning organization, are engaged with the basic resource of modern business, i.e. with knowledge and its utilization.

The learning banking industry is the result of a strategic relationship with the employee training and development and the recognition of the fact that knowledge is the answer to the numerous challenges from the environment. Every bank is becoming an institution that learns and teaches. The successful learning bank is able to attract the most talented people, to involve them into all business procedures and to motivate them to generate and exchange knowledge, enabling them in turn to maintain and improve their individual professional skills.

The study revealed that although all banks believe in the importance of the evaluation process they conduct somewhat limited evaluation processes for their T&D programmes. Despite regular evaluations of the T&D programmes these assessments are constrained to the use of questionnaires, asking trainees' managers or supervisors about their observation and assessments of trainees' learning. These methods of evaluating trainees are subjective in nature,

and indeed, supervisors' assessment for T&D effectiveness can be highly personalized.

In terms of the range of evaluation frameworks the Kirkpatrick evaluation model is mainly used by both public and private banks. Nevertheless, they depend to a very large extent on the reaction level, which is about the trainees' reaction, opinions, attitudes and satisfaction about the T&D programmes, followed by learning outcomes which they evaluate through asking the trainees' direct managers for their assessment of the trainees' learning. Thus, evaluation is mainly based on subjective assessments. These evaluations range across an individual's perceptions, opinions and attitudes toward T&D outcomes, rather than focusing on behavioural changes, organizational relevant work practices and operational improvements. T&D evaluation should not just be based on trainees' reactions, but rather it should be based on learning and behavioural outcomes, which could be gained from observing the trainees' performance after they complete T&D programmes. Two important behavioural outcomes that might be observed are whether they transfer what they learn from T&D into their workplaces; and the extent to which on the job performance was improved. Training evaluation faces many difficulties. A lack of quantitative measures, difficulty in measuring the change of trainees' behaviour over a short period of time, difficulty in separating training impact on the final results from the impacts of other activities, difficulty in getting managers to participate in the evaluation

process, lack of knowledge about evaluation, lack of job description, and time required to do evaluation are some other difficulties. These issues are exacerbated by a lack of well qualified people who are in

charge of T&D evaluation, lack of knowledge about the evaluation process and over dependency on external providers to evaluate the T & D programmes.

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